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Digital Advertising, Internet Advertising, Online Marketing, Web Advertising, Online Advertising, Internet Marketing, Web Marketing

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Abstract

This piece of research work aims at understanding the preferred emerging media options used for marketing. In the Internet age many new methods used for product promotion and marketing. "Desk research" has been turned into "online research", now in the online, market research has become possible. Many Indian companies are using digital marketing for competitive advantage. Social Media has quickly gained prominence as it provides people with the opportunity to communicate and share posts and topics. The development of information technology, followed by the advancement of digital communication tools, has encouraged businesses to change the way of communicating the product. Digital Marketing communications strategy is a strategy of using digital communication media. The purpose of the undertaken study is to examine the effectiveness of online digital media advertising and also about emerging media options used for marketing. This paper mainly studies the development history of digital marketing and existing significance including the difference and contact between digital marketing and traditional advertising and also the relationship between digital marketing and the Internet industry.

In this world of digitisation, digital marketing is a vogue that is sweeping across the whole world. The trend of digital marketing is growing day by day with the concepts of Internet marketing that is turning into an important platform of digital marketing along with the electronic gadgets like the digital billboards, mobile, tablets and smart phones, gaming consoles, and many such gadgets that help in digital marketing.

Keywords: SEO, AdWords, Pay Per Click, Google Analytics, Google Search Console, Digital Communication

Introduction

Digital marketing encompasses all marketing efforts that use an electronic device or internet. Businesses leverage digital channels such as search engines, social media, email and their websites to connect with current and prospective customers. This can also be referred as 'online marketing', 'internet marketing' or 'web marketing'. Digital marketing is defined by use of numerous digital tactics and channels to connect with customers where they spend much of their time: online. From website to business's online branding assets - digital advertising, email marketing, online brochures, and beyond -- there's spectrum of tactics falling under the umbrella of "digital marketing" Marketing is a restless, changing, and dynamic business activity.

Digital marketing is often referred to as 'online marketing', 'internet marketing' or 'web marketing'. The term digital marketing has grown in popularity over time, particularly in certain countries. In the USA online marketing is still prevalent, in Italy is referred as web marketing but in the UK and worldwide, digital marketing has become the most common term, especially after the year 2013.

Digital marketing is an umbrella term for the marketing of products or services using digital technologies, mainly on the Internet, but also including mobile phones, display advertising, and any other digital medium. The way in which digital marketing has developed since the 1990s and 2000s has changed the way brands and businesses utilize technology and digital marketing for their marketing. Digital marketing campaigns are becoming more prevalent as well as efficient, as digital platforms are increasingly incorporated into marketing plans and everyday life, and as people use digital devices instead of going to physical shops. 2. Objectives 1) The main purpose of this paper is to recognize the usefulness of digital marketing in the competitive market. 2) To study the impact of digital marketing on consumers purchase. 3. Methodology Applied

The customer also can ask queries or make suggestions about the business products and services. Medium of communication is generally phone calls, letters, and Emails. Medium of communication is mostly through social media websites, chat, and Email. Campaigning takes more time for designing, preparing, and launching. There is always a fast way to develop an online campaign and carry out changes along its development. With digital tools, campaigning is easier. It is carried out for a specific audience throughout from generating campaign ideas up to selling a product or a service.

Email Marketing

With email marketing a company can tailor its message to existing and potential customers this message might be as simple as coupon code product announcement or monthly newsletter. At a deeper level the email marketer is responsible for establishing an ongoing relationship between the company and its audience.

Email marketer need to work cross functionally with every marketing team to make sure that the email strategy is consistent with the organizations overall messaging the work relies heavily on data and email marketer need to closely monitor analytics related to email performance audience segmentation and A/B test.

Marketing communications

When the marketing team sets the marketing strategy marketing communications (sometimes abbreviated as “marcom”) is the team responsible for acting as the megaphone for the company message. Communications marketers work to enhance a company’s visibility in the market to customers, the public, the media, and sometimes to investors.

This essentially makes the communications manager the voice of the company. They work with designers, writers, and digital marketers to research the audience and create engaging pitches, compile analyst briefings, update their CRM, or talk with advertisers. Public relations is a facet of marketing communications as well, which means that the communications manager needs to foster relationships with the press.

Across channels:

- **Digital Marketing Manager** – Especially in smaller marketing teams, a digital marketing manager will be in charge of executing or delegating ABM, SEO, PPC, SEM, content, social, etc.
- **Demand Generation Manager** – Similar to a digital marketing manager, a demand generation manager will usually be in charge of SEO, PPC, SEM, and other channels.
- **Growth Marketing Manager** – Like the above two roles, a growth marketing manager wears a lot of hats, but is more data-driven and so probably only manages content that has SEO potential or paid promotion (not organic social).
- **Marketing Operations Manager** – In large marketing teams of 15+, this role is often needed to make sure projects are running smoothly.
- **Brand Manager** – In charge of making sure that anything the company puts out is on-brand, and might also drive key marketing strategies.
- **Marketing Project Manager** – As marketing teams grow, having a dedicated project manager to keep team-wide tasks on track can be a game-changer.
- **Content Marketing Manager** – In charge of strategizing, executing on, and delegating all forms of content, possibly including blogs, emails, social, and video.
- **Social Media Manager** – Creates content, manages team members or vendors, and strategically grows social accounts.
- **Social Media Coordinator** – Pretty much the same as above, but more likely to be used if there's a team of other social media marketers.
- **Product Marketing Manager** – This person can be managed by a more senior-level product marketer or could be the only product marketer on the team.
- **Paid Advertising Manager** – In charge of PPC, paid search, and paid social. Might manage advertising accounts, other team members, and/or freelancers and agencies.
- **Digital Advertising Manager** – This is essentially the same as above, but could lean more towards paid social.
- **Account-Based Marketing Manager** – Someone in this role focuses on leading the ABM program and reaching out to target accounts using both digital and offline channels.
- **Conversational Marketing Manager** – The person in this role is in charge of managing conversational marketers and/or building and optimizing chatbot software based on strategic decisions made with sales.
- **Events Marketing Manager** – Someone in this role is in charge of using events as a marketing channel, and making sure the event is successful, well-attended, and profitable.
- **Virtual Events Marketing Manager** – Similar to above, this person runs virtual events and summits in order to attract new customers.
- **Customer Marketing Manager** – Someone in this role is responsible for marketing to customers and turning customers into loyal, raving fans. This might include events management, customer-centric content creation, and other innovative tactics.
- **Paid Search Manager** – The paid search manager typically only manages Google and Bing ads.
- **SEO Manager** – An SEO manager might work in coordination with a content marketing manager or in place of one, if the primary content channel is SEO blogging. This person also ranks site pages.

- **Community Manager** – Community managers might focus mostly on social media community management or might also manage private groups and forums.
- **Partnership Manager** – A partnership manager brings in partner channels to grow the business. Typically this means that the partners are larger companies.
- **Affiliate Program Manager** – Similar to the above, but the partner revenue is more likely to be coming from individuals, influencers, and smaller companies.
- **Digital PR Manager** – With a lot of crossover between marketing and PR these days, you might be looking for someone to get your company featured on podcasts, blogs, online news sites, etc.

Literature Review

A number of research papers and articles provide a detailed insight on Internet Marketing. The findings from the literature are presented below:- Internet marketing has been described simply as ‘achieving marketing objectives through applying digital technologies’ (Chaffey et al., 2009). Digital marketing is the use of technologies to help marketing activities in order to improve customer knowledge by matching their needs (Chaffey, 2013). In the developed world, companies have realized the importance of digital marketing. In order for businesses to be successful they will have to merge online with traditional methods for meeting the needs of customers more precisely (Parsons, Zeisser, Waitman 1996). Introduction of new technologies has creating new business opportunities formarketers to manage their websites and achieve their business objectives (Kiani, 1998). Online advertising is a powerful marketing vehicle for building brands and increasing traffic for companies to achieve success (Song, 2001).

Expectations in terms of producing results and measuring success for advertisement money spent, digital marketing is more cost-efficient for measuring ROI on advertisement (Pepelnjak, 2008). Today, monotonous advertising and marketing techniques have given way to digital marketing. In addition, it is so powerful that it can help revive the economy and can create tremendous opportunities for governments to function in a more efficient manner (Munshi, 2012). Firms in Singapore have tested the success of digital marketing tools as being effective and useful for achieving results. (Teo, 2005). More importantly, growth in digital marketing has been due to the rapid advances in technologies and changing market dynamics (Mort, Sullivan, Drennan, Judy, 2002). In order for digital marketing to deliver result for businesses, digital content such as accessibility, navigation and speed are defined as the key characteristics for marketing (Kanttila, 2004). Other tried and tested tool for achieving success through digital marketing is the use of word-of-mouth WOM on social media and for making the site popular (Trusov, 2009). In addition, WOM is linked with creating new members and increasing traffic on the website which in return increases the visibility in terms of marketing. Social media with an extra ordinary example

Facebook has opened the door for businesses to communicate with millions of people about products and services and has opened new marketing opportunities in the market. This is possible only if the managers are fully aware of using the communication strategies to engage the customers and enhancing their experience (Mangold, 2009). Marketing professional must truly understand online social marketing campaigns and programs and understand how to do it effectively with

performance measurement indicators. As the market dynamics all over the world are changing in relation to the young audience accessibility to social media and usage. It is important that strategic integration approaches are adopted in organization's marketing communication plan (Rohm & Hanna, 2011). With the above reviews we can assume that GST is a tax reform which will change the scenario of the country as a support for this review study.

Pros and Cons of Digital Marketing

Digital marketing allows marketers to see accurate results in real time. If an advert is put in newspaper, it is difficult to estimate how many people actually flipped to that page and paid attention to ad. There's no surefire way to know if that ad was responsible for any sales at all. Yet digital marketing would help you to know reach for your product/service, to get engaged with prospective customers, to have global reach, to promote in personalized manner. However, with digital marketing have some setbacks .Digital marketing is highly dependent on the internet. Because internet may not be accessible in certain areas or consumers may have poor internet connection. It has lot of clutter, so marketers find it hard to make their advertisements stand out, and get consumers to start conversations about an organizations brand image or products.

Objective

The objectives of the research are

- To identify and understand the meaning of digital marketing
- To know about the role and importance of digital marketing as a communication system

The intention of this research is to find objectives, strategies and which indicators can be used by marketers to measure the ROI of their social media marketing objectives. The first objective of this research is to get a clear view of how the ROI in traditional marketing is measured and which objectives, strategies and indicators can be identified for social media marketing. Second objective is to reveal under experts whether the different identified objectives, strategies and indicators of the first objective (or which other) are usable and important for determining the ROI of social media marketing. The expected outcome of this research is an overview of appropriate objectives and strategies for social media marketing and which key indicators can determine the revenues and costs. Several objectives, strategies and indicators will be identified in this research based on existing literature. Research should address whether these objectives, strategies and indicators are practical useful according to experts and should reveal new insights for other objectives, strategies and indicators. The results can support and be used by marketers to define and measure the effectiveness of their social media marketing strategy.

Increase revenue

The primary goal of any marketing strategy is ultimately to increase revenue, and Internet marketing is no exception. Thankfully, the Internet provides plenty of opportunities for every business to improve their bottom line.

Build a brand

Internet marketing objectives often include building a brand. This means not only establishing your logo and company name in the minds of consumers, but also what your company stands for.

Improve local SEO

Many small businesses, as well as companies focused on increasing sales in specific geographic region, focus much of their marketing efforts on improving their local SEO. This means optimizing various elements on their sites in order to attract local customers who are looking for the services they provide.

Manage online reputation

In an age when anyone with a computer or smartphone can post their opinions about companies, products, and services for the whole world to see, it's important for businesses to maintain a solid online reputation. This means monitoring your company's name, maintaining social profiles, and responding to bad reviews accordingly.

Theory

Digital Marketing Tactics and Examples: Digital marketers are in charge of driving brand awareness and lead generation through all the digital channels -- both free and paid -- at company's disposal. These channels include social media, the company's own website, search engine rankings, email, display advertising, and the company's blog. The digital marketer focuses on different key performance indicator (KPI) for each channel so they can properly measure the company's performance across each one. Digital marketing is carried out across many marketing roles today. In small companies, one generalist might own many of the digital marketing tactics described above at the same time. In larger companies, these tactics have multiple specialists that each focus on just one or two of the brand's digital channels.

Search Engine Optimization (SEO)

Search Engine Optimization, more commonly known as SEO, is one of the most used digital marketing techniques. It is optimizing your online presence- particularly your website for search engines.

This is done so that when any person in searching for your business or any relevant keywords in any search engine, your website ranks at the top. It is generally divided into two parts- on-page SEO which deals with optimizing your webpages for the search engines and off-page SEO which includes backlinks (other websites pointing to your website), social signals, etc.

Social Media Marketing

This is another most common way of online marketing. In this, you utilize social networks like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, etc. to reach out to your prospective customers. Almost all internet users have their own accounts on at least one social network. So you have a very vast pool of users to target for your business.

The advantage of this medium is that any person with basic internet skills can manage basic social media marketing like making company profiles on these networks, posting regularly, engaging with followers and loyal customers, etc. Slightly complex things like running paid advertisements on these platforms might require expert knowledge.

Paid Advertising

Paid Advertising is one of the quickest ways to reach our to your desired target audience and market your products or services. You just need to make an ad, select the target audience based on location, demographics, interest, etc., assign campaign budget and you are good to go.

One of the most famous paid advertising platforms in Google Adwords. You can use Google Adwords to show advertisements on search pages, their partner publishers, Youtube, etc. Facebook, Twitter, Linkedin, Quora, and many other social networks offer paid advertising.

Affiliate Marketing

Affiliate Marketing is simply third-party affiliates doing marketing of your products or services for a certainly fixed commission. The commission can be a certain fixed percentage on the total revenue generated via affiliates or a fixed cost for every sale.

This is a very good medium which can generate decent growth in sales for you provided you use the correct approach. Since a third party affiliate is doing promotions in exchange for a fixed cost per sale, the chances of the marketing spend happening without customer acquisition or sale is nil.

Native Advertising

Native advertising refers to advertisements that are primarily content-led and featured on a platform alongside other, non-paid content. Buzz Feed-sponsored posts are a good example, but many people also consider social media advertising to be "native" – Face book advertising and Instagram advertising.

Marketing Automation

Marketing automation refers to the software that serves to automate your basic marketing operations. Many marketing departments can automate repetitive tasks they would otherwise do manually, such as Email newsletters, Social media post scheduling, Contact list updating, Lead-nurturing workflows, Campaign tracking and reporting.

Pay-Per-Click (PPC)

PPC is a method of driving traffic to your website by paying a publisher every time your ad is clicked. One of the most common types of PPC is Google Ad Words, which allows you to pay for top slots on Google's search engine results pages at a price "per click" of the links you place. Other channels where you International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (IJTSRD) use PPC mainly include Paid ads on Face book, Promoted Tweets on Twitter, Sponsored Messages on LinkedIn.

Email Marketing

Companies use email marketing as a way of communicating with their audiences. Email is often used to promote content, discounts and events, as well as to direct people toward the business's website. The types of emails you might send in an email marketing campaign include Blog subscription newsletters, Follow-up emails to website visitors who downloaded something, Customer welcome emails, Holiday promotions to loyalty program members, Tips or similar series emails for customer nurturing.

Inbound Marketing

Inbound marketing refers to the "full-funnel" approach to attracting, engaging, and delighting customers using online content. You can use every digital marketing tactic listed above throughout an inbound marketing strategy.

Online PR

Online PR is practice of securing earned online coverage with digital publications, blogs, and other content-based websites. It's much like traditional PR, but in the online space. The channels you can use to maximize your PR efforts include: Reporter outreach via social media Engaging online reviews of your company, Engaging comments on your personal website or blog.

Digital Marketing – a boost to today's businesses

Regardless of what your company sells, digital marketing still involves building out buyer's personas to identify your audience's needs and creating valuable online content.

B2B Digital Marketing

If company is business-to-business (B2B), digital marketing efforts are likely to be centered on online lead generation, with end goal being for someone to speak to salesperson. The role of your marketing strategy is to attract and convert highest quality leads for salespeople via your website and supporting digital channels. Beyond website, you'll probably choose to focus efforts on business-focused channels like LinkedIn where your demographic is spending their time online.

B2C Digital Marketing

If your company is business-to-consumer (B2C), depending on price point of products, the goal of digital marketing efforts is to attract people to website and have they become customers without ever needing to speak to salesperson. For that reason, you're probably less likely to focus on 'leads' in their traditional sense, and more likely to focus on building an accelerated buyer's journey, from the moment someone lands on your website, to moment that they make a purchase. This will often mean your product features in your content higher up in the marketing funnel than it might for a B2B business, and you might need to use stronger calls-to-action (CTAs). For B2C companies, channels like Instagram and Pinterest are more valuable than business-focused platforms LinkedIn.

C2C Digital Marketing

Customer to customer (C2C) is a business model whereby customers can trade with each other, typically in an online environment. Two implementations of C2C markets are auctions and classified advertisements. C2C marketing has soared in popularity with the arrival of the Internet and companies such as eBay, Etsy, and Craigslist.

Website Traffic

You can see the exact number of people who have viewed your website's homepage in real time by using digital analytics software, available in marketing platforms like Hub Spot. Also how many pages they visited, what device they were using, and where they came from, amongst other digital analytics data.

Attribution Modeling

An effective digital marketing strategy combined with right tools and technologies allows to trace all sales back to customer's first digital touch point with your business is called attribution modeling. It allows identifying trends in the way people research and buying your product, helping you to make more informed decisions about what parts of your marketing strategy deserve more attention, and what parts of your sales cycle need refining.

Online behavioral advertising

It is the practice of collecting information about a user's online activity over time, "on a particular device and across different, unrelated websites, in order to deliver advertisements tailored to that user's interests and preferences.

Collaborative Environment

A collaborative environment can be set up between the organization, technology service provider, and digital agencies to optimize effort, resource sharing, reusability and communications. Organizations are inviting their customers to help them better understand how to service them.

Data-driven advertising

Users generate lot of data in every step they take on the path of customer journey and Brands can now use that data to activate their known audience with data-driven programmatic media International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development.

Remarketing

Remarketing plays a major role in digital marketing. This tactic allows marketers to publish targeted ads in front of an interest category or defined audiences, generally called searchers in web speak, they have either searched for particular products or services or visited a website for some purpose.

Game advertising

Game ads are advertisements that exist within computer or video games. One of the most common examples of in-game advertising is billboards appearing in sports games. In-game ads also might appear as brand-name products like guns, cars, or clothing that exist as gaming status symbols.

Ease of access

A key objective is engaging digital marketing customers and allowing them to interact with brand through servicing and delivery of digital media. Users with access to Internet can use many digital mediums, such as Face book, YouTube, Forums, and Email etc.

Interactive Marketing

Make sure your advertising strategy engages the potential customer in a conversation. According to a survey by ExpoTV.com, 55 percent respondents preferred to have ongoing communications with the companies they buy from; and 89 percent felt more loyal to the companies if they were invited to provide feedback. Use tools like widgets and opt-in features to make your website interactive, solicit feedback and track user behavior. Engage with the customers actively and customize offers based on their preferences and browsing activities.

Limitations of the study

Based on this study, it can further be argued that knowing which social media sites a company's target market utilizes is another key factor in guaranteeing that online marketing will be successful. The effectiveness of Internet marketing with respect to different business can be analyzed. The study can further be extended to compare the internet marketing techniques with specific to various businesses.

Methodology of the study

Every marketer will agree that marketing strategies are very valuable. Revenue figures may vary depending on the investments that a business makes. However, it is a no-brainer that marketing plays a significant role in the success of a business, whether big or small. Consider small businesses that use 1% of their income on average, for marketing.

Website Optimization

If you are a serious contender in the marketing world, you must have a website to supplement your social media pages. The website must have a proper design because, in the first place, it reflects the image of your company. Website optimization involves designing a website from nothing. It involves adding keywords or phrases, image tags; editing Metadata to ensure that your site is accessible to a search engine.

Social media

We are in a digital age, where information and knowledge are everywhere. Comparing with old marketing methods, the internet is a big smile and a perfect strategy to reach out to new customer

horizons hitherto unimagined. Social media is an evergreen marketing strategy because most people and especially millennials tend to follow a brand on social media. A bigger percentage of social media users will recommend a service or a product if they are satisfied with its social media service.

Direct mail

If you send thank you cards to your customers for showing appreciation, they are more likely to purchase your products again. Consumers interested in your industry will take information leaflets very seriously and provide expert advice. Remember you have to use high-quality prints to impress your clients, and if this is a hassle, stick to direct mails. It is a pronounced way of making sure that your customers are always aware should there be any new product or service from your business.

Television Advertisements

Television is a powerful way of communicating to the masses. It earns a slot in the evergreen strategy because advertising on tv is far much better than and effective than placing an add on a newspaper. A TV ad that appears during prime time hours will reach more audiences in a matter of seconds, thereby creating awareness of the existence of a service or a product. You can never go wrong with a television ad, however annoying it might be simply because it will still serve its objective, which is entering the minds of potential customers.

Speaking engagements and networking

One of the advantages of using speaking engagements is that you are directly speaking to a targeted audience. Their attention tells you they are interested in what you are offering and you will need only a small, professional, and spirited nudge to turn them into your consumers. Speaking engagements are a perfect marketing strategy that has the power to generate good leads. Talk of the good old word of mouth working for the best interest of your business.

Research Methodology:

A. Research Design: Descriptive

Sampling Design

- i) Population : customers and retailers of Varanasi city Sample Size :200 customers and 200 retailer

B. Sampling Technique: Stratified random Sampling.

C. Data sources

- a) Primary Source: Primary data will be collected through Customers and retailers of Varanasi city through self-developed questionnaire as the method described in sampling procedure section.
- b) Secondary Source: Secondary data will be collected through research papers, Magazines, newspaper, articles and etc.

D. Data collection tools

A self-developed non disguised questionnaire will be used for primary data collection.

E. Statistical techniques

Various statistical test (parametric and non para metric test) and software (SPSS, Structural Equation Modeling) will be used according to the fulfillment of the research objectives.

F. Hypothesis Testing:

A hypothesis test examines two mutually exclusive claims about a parameter to determine which is best supported by the sample data. The parameter is usually the mean or proportion of some population variable of importance to the marketer.

Limitations of the study

1. Biasedness of the researcher
2. Specific to the Varanasi Location
3. Can't generalized
4. Respondent biasedness (not required)

Scope Of Digital Marketing

Before we delve into the scope of digital marketing in India, let's understand the importance of digital marketing. Today, almost everyone is online.

Images of Digital Marketing

Conclusion suggestions and recommendations

Three technological trends the ubiquity of information in digital form the widespread use of computer network and the rapid proliferation of the World Wide Web—have profound implications for the way intellectual property (IP) is created, distributed, and accessed by virtually every sector of society. The stakes are high in terms of both ideology and economics

Result

Most businesses these days have integrated at least some kind of digital marketing solutions into their overall marketing strategy however digital marketing often needs a budget and it turns out employers don't think to dish out money for some think that doesn't prove its birth even if employers are invested in digital marketing with or without results it's important for marketers to know how their campaign hyper for me to be able to make adjustment that will bring in more leads

Here's the thing: only 29% of marketers believe they are measuring their marketing performance well. It doesn't have to be that way – marketers on any budget can successfully and effectively measure their digital marketing results.

WHERE TO BEGIN:

Before measuring anything, you should understand why you're measuring. Set some goals for your organization. Are you trying to build awareness? Get more sales leads? Engage more with your customers? Define a couple goals that you want to reach, and that will help you define what numbers you should be measuring. Once these goals are set, create Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for each of these goals. By doing this, you are defining what is valuable to your company. For example: if awareness is a top priority, you should set a goal for site visits, and then try to beat those goals month to month.

Below are some KPI's that you should consider setting for your organization:

Site Traffic: Of the most obvious metrics to measure, a marketer should not only track the traffic. How many people are coming to your site and engaging with it? How many pages are they browsing? This is the baseline number for all your site visits and each of your pages.

New vs. Returning Traffic: Is your information valuable to your site visitors and are you building relationships with them by getting them to come back to your site? This number can tell you.

Mobile Traffic: We all know that mobile has reached the tipping point to overtake desktop search, so make sure that your site and your content is mobile-optimized to reach your audience.

Site Sources: Not only can analytics tell you how much traffic is coming to your site, but it can tell you what people are coming to see. This is valuable because you can understand what content is performing well and what content could use some work.

Average Time on Page: This number will show if visitors are consuming the content for the appropriate length of time and help show if content is relevant to the audience.

Bounce Rate: Going hand-in-hand with average time on page, the bounce rate shows if someone jumps on the site, then leaves without looking at other pages on the site – an indication that content might need work.

Conversion Rate: This measures the effectiveness of email campaigns by showing how many recipients took an action, and what sources are converting to leads.

Number of Leads: Every form that is filled on a company's website should be tracked. The more information that is collected through the forms, the easier it is to segment leads to marketers know where to focus their attention.

Search Engine Rankings: the mother of all KPI's – you want to make every effort to boost your search engine rankings through SEO and SEM tactics. Good rankings deliver good traffic to your website, which often translates into sales leads.

Traditional Marketing versus Digital Marketing

Traditional marketing is the most recognizable form of marketing. Traditional marketing is non-digital way used to promote the product or services of business entity. On the other hand, digital marketing is the marketing of products or services using digital channels to reach consumers. Some comparisons are presented below: digital marketing review.

Traditional Marketing versus Digital Marketing Comparison

Traditional Marketing	Digital Marketing
Traditional marketing includes print, broadcast, direct mail, and telephone	Digital marketing includes online advertising, email marketing, social media, text messaging, affiliate marketing, search engine optimization, pay per click
No interaction with the audience	Interaction with the audience
Results are easy to measure	Results are to a great extent easy to measure
Advertising campaigns are planned over a long period of time	Advertising campaigns are planned over short period of time
Expensive and time-consuming process	Reasonably cheap and rapid way to promote the products or services
Success of traditional marketing strategies can be celebrated if the firm can reach large local audience	Success of digital marketing strategies can be celebrated if the firm can reach some specific number of local audiences.

One campaign prevails for a long time	Campaigns can be easily changed with ease and innovations can be introduced within any campaign
Limited reach to the customer due to limited number of customer technology	Wider reach to the customer because of the use of various customers technology
24/7 year-round exposure is not possible	24/7 year-round exposure is possible
No ability to go viral	Ability to go viral
One way conversation	Two ways conversation
Responses can only occur during work hours	Response or feedback can occur anytime

IMPACT ON BUSINESS IN POST COVID SCENARIO

There are many stats that highlight the importance of digital marketing. With global eCommerce sales expected to reach \$4.5 trillion by 2021, it's clear that there's significant potential for online promotional activity. What's more, 51% of shoppers research their purchases on Google before making them.

We've also seen how vital online shopping is in the first half of 2020. At the peak of the COVID-19 lockdown in the UK, online orders were up 200% compared to the previous year. For all kinds of companies, digital marketing and the sales it generated were a lifeline when stores were closed.

Findings

Perhaps, the most important aspect of your Digital Marketing is Web Analytics. Essentially, Web Analytics helps you to collect, measure, understand, analyze, plan, report and predict the web activities for your business. Web Analytics should not be confused with Web Statistics. As opposed to simple reporting, Web Analytics gives you analyses and different angles to ponder vis-à-vis your business. Some of the important Web Analytics tools are Google Analytics, Spring Metrics, Woopra, Clicky, Mint and Chartbeat. It goes without saying that every advertiser should use Web Analytics to understand his business and improve the ROI and conversions.

Conclusions and Implications

We experience a radical change in India towards the digitalization. The consumer are looking and searching more on internet to find the best deal form the sellers around India as compared to traditional or conventional methods. Cha (2009) also established in his study that more people perceive shopping services on social networking sites as useful and easy to use, the more likely they are willing to shop for items on social networks. The wide range of consumers utilizing social networks means that most target markets can be reached (Cha 2009). Shankar (et al. 2011) also revealed in his study that more shoppers are using social media (e.g., Twitter, Facebook, MySpace, and LinkedIn) and rely on them for marketing shopping decisions; promotion through these media

has become important. In this study, we acknowledged that businesses can really benefit from Digital marketing such as search engine optimization (SEO), search engine marketing (SEM), content marketing, influencer marketing, content automation, e-commerce marketing, campaign marketing, and social media marketing, social media optimization, e-mail direct marketing, display advertising, e-books, optical disks and games and are becoming more and more common in our advancing technology. Vogus (2011) also determined that large companies are regarding social media sites as strategic tools and some businesses are even hiring employees to oversee their social media pages. Mangold and Faulds (2009) recommended that social media should be regarded as an integral part of an organization's integrated marketing strategy and should not be taken lightly.

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